

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE ACQUISITION IN HIGHER EDUCATION: EVALUATING PEDAGOGICAL BENEFITS, RISKS, AND INSTRUCTIONAL IMPLICATIONS

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The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into people's lives has dramatically changed how we work, study, and interact across contexts. Apart from changing individuals' perspectives on daily tasks and activities, it is obvious that AI has prompted educators to redesign their curriculum development, teaching approaches, and assessment processes. AI has become a reason for the creation of a new field, Artificial Intelligence in Education (AIED), expanding opportunities for learning with the help of AI-driven personal instructions, AI-powered exploratory learning, the analysis of students' written works, and chatbots that support students [4].

English language instruction has already been interrupted by this tendency, which has brought both positive changes in the field and some negative impact. In the current ever-changing environment, language instructors have a need to adapt to the widespread implementation of AI technologies and mindfully integrate them into their language teaching process, especially in the context of higher education, where students have a broad awareness of AI usage. In the context of English language instruction, AI-powered tools ranging from automated writing assistants to adaptive learning platforms are reshaping traditional pedagogical frameworks.

While these technologies create innovative ways to facilitate learning outcomes, they also raise critical questions regarding academic integrity, learner autonomy, and the evolving role of educators. This paper examines Artificial Intelligence's role in language education, including its advantages, possible pitfalls, and how it can be applied in the language teaching context in higher education institutions.

Literature Review

The growing number of literature on AIED highlights both its transformative potential and possible disadvantages. AI tools used in language acquisition provide personalized feedback, student-tailored content, as well as real-time interaction, which engages learners and enhances their learning outcomes [3]. In addition, AI tools have been shown to facilitate autonomous learning. According to Chen, AI support enables learners to flexibly adjust their learning objectives, strategies, and pace based on feedback information [2]. In other words, AI systems optimize students' learning by offering personalized pathways.

On the other hand, researchers also raise concerns about the implications of AI use in language education. One major issue is the over-reliance on AI tools that results in the degradation of critical thinking abilities [7]. Furthermore, ethical concerns, namely data privacy and algorithmic bias, have been widely discussed, particularly in relation to the collection and utilization of student-related data.

Benefits of AI in English Language Education

As discussed above, one of the most notable advantages of AI in language acquisition is its ability to provide personalized learning opportunities to learners [4]. AI-powered adaptive learning tools tailor content based on student performance, ensuring that learners progress at an appropriate pace. This aspect is

particularly essential in diverse classrooms where students have various language proficiency levels.

The second advantage of AI-based systems in language learning is the availability of immediate feedback. AI-powered platforms such as Grammarly, Duolingo, and Elsa Speak provide quick feedback on grammar use, correctness of pronunciation, range of vocabulary, speaking accuracy, and writing structure, thus making it easy for learners to work on mistakes. Despite the fact that instant feedback provided by AI platforms is highly appreciated by learners, they constantly report that these tools have limitations connected to creativity and coherence evaluation [1]

The next positive aspect of AI use in language learning is enhanced language practice. AI tools enable continuous practice beyond the classroom. Applications such as Elsa Speak, Learn AI, and speech recognition software help learners improve pronunciation and learn to speak smoothly, whilst AI chatbots, namely ChatGPT or Gemini, simulate real-life conversations, enhancing communicative competence.

AI use in language education provides assistance for educators as well. Automation of repetitive tasks such as grading or correcting errors reduces teachers' workload enabling them to focus more on higher-order teaching activities that include critical thinking development and personalized guiding and mentoring students. AI-driven intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) have played an essential role in education administration by utilizing AI-based solutions that streamline routine processes, give real-time analytics, and support data-informed decision-making [5].

Drawbacks and possible challenges of AI for language learners and educators

AI-generated content poses a challenge to traditional assessment methods by raising concerns about academic integrity. Students may complete assignments and projects fully relying on AI assistance, which in turn leads to plagiarism-related concerns. In order to avoid academic misconduct, universities may invest on platforms that detect cheating, develop clear academic integrity policy and provide in-service training for teachers on AI-made assignments detection [6]. Apart from work authenticity-related issues, over-dependence on AI may limit students' cognitive capability. When learners constantly seek AI help to generate ideas or correct mistakes, they may not develop essential analytical and problem-solving skills.

Another concern regarding AI use in language education is connected to the digital inequality issue. Not all educational establishments have equal access to AI tools. Students from disadvantages backgrounds tend to face barriers in the utilization of advanced digital and AI-based technologies, which may results in disparities in learning outcomes.

Last but not least important pitfall of AI systems is related to ethical or privacy-oriented challenges. The vast majority of AI tools require access to user private data, raising serious considerations about data security in cases of system outage and user data misuse. Furthermore, algorithmic bias can affect the fairness and accuracy of AI-generated feedback and assistance.

Instructional Implications

By automating the completion of repetitive tasks, AI redefines teachers' roles in the classroom from knowledge providers to facilitators. This role involves guiding students in the effective and ethical use of AI tools to maximize language learning outcomes and avoid plagiarism cases. In this context, serious

responsibility lies on teachers, as they will be not only responsible for promoting AI tools, but also training learners on the responsible use of AI by enhancing their digital literacy, including the understanding of AI limitations, recognizing biases, and maintaining academic integrity.

As over-reliance of students on AI tools made the assessment process complicated, it became obvious that traditional written tasks need to be substituted with process-based ones, such as oral presentations, project-based activities, and tasks that require reflection to ensure authenticity of work during the assessment.

Additionally, educators should incorporate AI tools strategically into lesson planning. The whole lesson can not be built around AI tools, their use need to be controlled and planned thoroughly, such as using AI for formative assessment, language practice, and personalized learning. Human-led instruction should always be prioritized [4].

Conclusion

In higher education institutions, AI is a valuable tool in modern pedagogy, personalizing learning, providing timely feedback, and supporting teachers. However, its integration must be approached with caution to address challenges related to academic integrity, equity, and ethical considerations.

Further research activities should focus on developing frameworks for the responsible use of AI in higher education and exploring its long-term impacts on student learning outcomes. A key idea that should always be promoted is that the goal of AI tools is not to replace human educators but to enhance the teaching and learning experience through strategic and proper use of AI.

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